

Controlled Hydrothermal Synthesis of Nano-MoO₂ as Anode for Lithium Ion Battery

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Abstract

Objectives/methods: Nano-MoO₂, with different allotropic forms is synthesized through a reduction reaction of molybdenum trioxide in aqueous solutions using ethylene glycol. The structure and morphology characterizations are carried out by XRD, SEM, and Raman. The XRD and SEM data indicate the as-prepared samples present a single and homogeneous phase MoO₂ with monocline symmetry. **Findings/application:** The optical properties of the as-synthesized samples are investigated by photoluminescence. Cyclic voltammetric characterization of MoO₂ films has revealed reversible redox behavior with charge–discharge cycling which corresponds to the reversible lithium intercalation/deintercalation. The electrochemical properties study of the MoO₂ has showed that the monoclinic MoO₂ has a good stability and a nice reversibility, an indicator that the molybdenum dioxide is most suitable for application in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs).

Keywords: Hydrothermal Treatment; Electrode Materials; Electrochemical Properties; Lithium-ion Batteries.

1. Introduction

Transition metal oxides have been widely studied because of its large applications [1–6]. Among these oxides, molybdenum dioxide (MoO₂) shows mainly rich chemistry because of the variable molybdenum oxidation state and its flexible coordination environment [7–8]. Due to their low cost and good electronic conductivity, MoO₂ can also constitute a good electrochemical capacitors and electrode materials for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) [9–17]. Molybdenum dioxide exists in various polymorphic forms which depend on thermodynamic conditions: hexagonal phase (P63/mmc), tetragonal phase (P42/mnm), and monoclinic phase (P2₁/n) [18–20].

Usually, MoO₂ is obtained through a reduction process MoO₃ at a high temperature in the presence of hydrogen [7], but their results exhibited a limited success because only nano-sized powders in zero dimensions were prepared. Hydrothermal treatment involving the reduction of MoO₃ to MoO₂ offers a new approach to synthesis of nano-materials in one, two, or three dimensions under mild conditions, which offers various morphologies and an easy control. In Ref. [21], Zhang et al. have described the synthesis of MoO₂ powders with spheres morphology by a reduction process of the molybdenum trioxide in the presence of diethylenetriamine (DETA). Moreover, Zhang et al. [22] prepared MoO₂ nanosheets via a one-pot solvothermal approach, using an ionic liquid in the reaction system. The authors have studied the electrochemical properties of MoO₂ nanosheets. In fact, this study proves that the MoO₂ can be used as anode materials for Li-ion intercalation because a large reversible capacity, a high rate performance, and a good cycling stability. Obviously, the electrochemical performance of molybdenum dioxide depends on several parameters, including the morphology, the deposition method, the film thickness, the electrolytic medium, and the scan rate. In [23] this study, we expect the same behavior but and in besides these parameters, we studied also the effect on the morphologies of the MoO₂ and the influence of the allotropic forms on the electroactivity of the molybdenum dioxide.

In this study, we described an easy and a low-cost hydrothermal treatment for the synthesis of MoO₂ nanostructured by using MoO₃, as a molybdenum source, and ethylene glycol (C₂H₆O₂), as a reducing and structure-directing agent. By varying the synthesis temperature, duration and molar ration a structural change of the MoO₂ phase is observed. The electrochemical properties of the MoO₂ have been investigated using cyclic voltammetry (CV) in the presence of Li⁺ in propylene carbonate electrolytic. The influence of the morphology and the allotropic forms of the MoO₂ is discussed. Despite the diversity of synthetic methods of the MoO₂ phase, our study presents a new strategy to get the phase MoO₂ while controlling the morphology and the allotropic form of the MoO₂ phase.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Hydrothermal Synthesis

Nano-MoO₂ particles were synthesized through hydrothermal method. All the chemical reagents were purchased from Acros Organics and used without further purification. Molybdenum (+VI) oxide (MoO₃) was used as molybdenum source; ethylene glycol has been used as template. In a typical synthesis, the preparation was made from a mixture of MoO₃, ethylene glycol, and distilled water (5 mL) in a molar ratio of 1:1:385. Reactants were introduced in this order and stirred for a few minutes before introducing the resulting suspension in a Teflon-lined steel autoclave and the temperature set for 4 days at different temperatures. The pH of the solution keeps close to pH = 7 during the whole synthesis. To remove organics residues, the obtained powder was washed with ethanol. It was then dried at 80 °C to lead to a black powder, which suggests that Mo⁶⁺ ions have been totally reduced to Mo⁴⁺ through the decomposition of the organic compound.

2.2. Characterization Techniques

The black powders structure was characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis (Philips PW 1820, Instrument, 2θ ranging from 20 to 60° and $\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha 1} = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded with a SEI instrument (operating at 5 kV) microscope. Raman spectroscopy was performed using a Jobin Yvon T 64 000 spectrometer (blue laser excitation with 488 nm wavelength and <55 mW power at the sample). To investigate the optical properties of the samples, photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy was performed using a 250 mm Jobin Yvon luminescence spectrometer.

2.3. Electrochemical Measurements

The electrodes were fabricated by blending MoO_2 with acetylene black carbon as conductive additive and polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF), in a weight ratio of 8/1/1, respectively. Homogenous, thick slurry was prepared using N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) as solvent for the mixture. The slurry was cast on a Cu metal foil and dried in vacuum oven for 12 h at 90 °C. The coin-type cells CR2032 were assembled using the as-prepared electrode as the work electrode; a layer of metallic lithium pasted on the stainless steel disk was used as counter as well as reference electrode. The electrolyte consists of 1 M LiPF_6 in mixed ethylene carbonate (EC) and diethyl carbonate (DEC) (the volume ratio of EC to DEC is 1:1). Cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments were performed in the voltage range of 3.0–0.0 V vs Li/Li^+ using a Biologic VMP-3 model. The electrochemical charge–discharge tests were evaluated at various current rates in a voltage cut off of 3.0 and 0.0 V vs Li/Li^+ .

3. Results and Discussion

The first study deals with the composition, structural characterization and the structural transformation of the black powders obtained by the hydrothermal method in the presence of ethylene glycol were determined by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD). The phase of the resulting products obtained from the reducing of the MoO_3 by ethylene glycol at 180 °C for different durations (1 day, 2 and 4 days), as shown in Figure 1. It is noted that the crystalline phases for molybdenum oxide are discriminatory at different reaction times. Indeed, after one and two days of synthesis process (Figure 1a and b), the diffraction pattern shows the presence of the monoclinic MoO_2 (JCPDS data file 00-032-0671, $P2_1/n$ space group) with lattice parameters $a = 0.5606 \text{ nm}$, $b = 0.4859 \text{ nm}$, and $c = 0.5537 \text{ nm}$. When the reaction time is increased to 4 days (Figure 1c), we notice that there is a structural change and that the all diffraction peaks can perfectly indexed to the hexagonal MoO_2 crystalline phase with $a = 0.2838 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 0.4720 \text{ nm}$, according to JCPDS# 50-0739, $P63/mmc$ space group. No peaks of any other phases or impurities were observed from the XRD patterns, indicating that the monoclinic and hexagonal molybdenum dioxide crystalline phase with high purity could be obtained using the present synthetic process. This study demonstrates the impact of the hydrothermal reaction time on the crystalline and structure transformation of the molybdenum dioxide.

FIGURE 1. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the black powders synthesized at 180 °C for (a) 1 day, (b) 2 days, and (c) 4 days.

Various experiments were performed to investigate the effect of modifications to the hydrothermal treatment on the structure and the morphology of the final product. The samples were prepared at different temperatures (140 °C, 180 °C, and 220 °C). At 140 °C (Figure 2a), the diffraction pattern shows the presence of monoclinic MoO₂ (m-MoO₂) (JCPDS data file 00-032-0671, P2₁/n space group). When the temperature increases from 140 to 180 and 220 °C (Figure 2b and c), we notice the disappearance of the peaks characteristic of the monoclinic form and the appearance of the new peaks of high intensity, which are perfectly indexed to the hexagonal MoO₂ (h-MoO₂).

In the remainder of this study, we will be studying the optical and electrochemical properties of two different allotropic forms of the MoO₂ phase (the hexagonal h-MoO₂ phase and the monoclinic m-MoO₂one) synthesized for 4 days at 140 °C, 180 °C, and 220 °C.

The morphology of synthesized materials was studied using the SEM. Figure 3 shows SEM images of the powder (m-MoO₂ and h-MoO₂) synthesized through a hydrothermal method. Monoclinic m-MoO₂ exhibited a hierarchical and homogenous phases with

FIGURE 2. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the black powders synthesized at 4 days for (a) 140 °C, (b) 180 °C, and (c) 220 °C.

FIGURE 3. SEM of the MoO₂ powders synthesized for 4 days at (a, b) 140 °C, (c, d) 180 °C, and (e, f) 220 °C.

isotropic crystallite shapes (Figure 3a and b). From the hexagonal phase synthesized at 180 °C (Figure 3c and d), we notice the presence of irregular particles with irregular size, whereas uniform nanospheres were observed (Figure 3e and f) for product obtained after the lapse of 4 days at 220 °C. The hexagonal MoO₂, synthesized at 220 °C, SEM images show a homogenous phase with uniform nanospheres. These results corroborate that the temperature has a pivotal effect on molybdenum nanomaterials structure and morphology.

The structure of MoO₂ nanoparticles was even more characterized by Raman spectroscopy. A typical room temperature Raman spectroscopy of the m-MoO₂ synthesized at 140 °C and h-MoO₂ synthesized at 180 and 220 °C shown in Figure 4. The monoclinic phase (m-MoO₂) indicates the presence of two intense peaks located at 817 cm⁻¹ (A_g, γ_s mode) and 990 cm⁻¹ (A_g, γ_{as} mode) which are assigned to the stretching mode of M=O. From the h-MoO₂, many characteristic peaks are observed, representing O=M=O wagging (290 cm⁻¹), O-M-O bend (340 cm⁻¹), O-M-O stretch (670 cm⁻¹), M=O stretch (817 cm⁻¹, A_g, ν_s) and M=O (990 cm⁻¹, A_g, ν_{as}) stretch, respectively.

The photoluminescence spectra of m-MoO₂ and h-MoO₂ are shown in Figure 5. The three samples exhibit strong PL intensity at about 350 nm, which means a prompt recombination of electrons in the conduction band and holes in the valence band.

To evaluate the stability and the electrochemical performances of the h-MoO₂ as electrode material in batteries lithium ion, cyclic voltammetry analysis was conducted. Figure 6a shows the CVs curves of h-MoO₂ between 0.0 and 3.0 V at 0.1 mV s⁻¹. One reduction peak (0.7 V) and two oxidation peaks (1.3 V and 1.7 V) were observed in the first cycle. The charge measured for reduction process is equal to the charge measured for oxidation (Q_{ox}/Q_{red} = 99%) (shown in Figure 6b). This indicates that all the Li⁺ cation

FIGURE 4. Raman spectra of the MoO₂ powders synthesized for 4 days at (a) 140 °C, (b) 180 °C, and (c) 220 °C.

inserted in the h-MoO₂ electrode during the reduction process are totally expelled after material oxidation and that the Li⁺ intercalation/de-intercalation is totally reversible at 0.1 mV/s scan rate. Figure 5c shows the charge–discharge curves of the h-MoO₂ for the first and second cycles at a current density of 100 mA g⁻¹. It can be found that the material display the discharge and charge capacities of 345 mAh g⁻¹ and 250 mAh g⁻¹, respectively at the first cycle. As for the second cycle, the discharge and charge capacities of h-MoO₂ are 250 and 248 mAh g⁻¹. The initial capacities loss of 95 mAh g⁻¹ due to the formation of solid electrolyte interface (SEI) layer. Figure 6d shows the cycling performances of the h-MoO₂ electrode. As expected, under the rate of 100 mA g⁻¹, the h-MoO₂ electrode shows a high discharge capacity (360 mAh g⁻¹) and maintains 255 mAh g⁻¹ after 50 cycles. The electrochemical performance of the h-MoO₂ nanoparticle is attributed to the nanospheres structure with small diameter and efficient one-dimensional electron transport pathways.

FIGURE 5. Photoluminescence spectra of the MoO₂ powders synthesized for 4 days at (a) 140 °C, (b) 180 °C, and (c) 220 °C.

FIGURE 6. (a) CV curves of h-MoO₂ electrode; (b) Coulombic efficiency of h-MoO₂ electrode (c) charge/discharge voltage profiles of h-MoO₂ at a current density of 0.1 A g⁻¹, and (d) the specific capacity of the h-MoO₂.

4. Conclusion

We have successfully controlled synthesized m-MoO₂ and h-MoO₂ via an easy hydrothermal way from the mixture of MoO₃ and ethylene glycol under soft conditions. The hydrothermal conditions, as duration and temperature, played an important role in the structure and the morphology of the final product. The h-MoO₂ electrode demonstrated (a) high reversible capacity, (b) excellent cycling performance, and (c) good rate capacity as an anode electrode material for Li-ion batteries.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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